

METHODS OF DESIGNING PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATIONS IN URBAN AND RURAL AREAS

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Annotation: This article describes the architectural appearance of preschool educational organizations, taking into account their natural environment, compositional solutions, and methods of their architectural design. The main requirements and conditions for the organization of a favorable environment are analyzed.

Key words: environment; coverage radius; city; neighborhood; village; preschool organization; architecture; design styles.

Introduction. Preschool educational organizations, being a material reflection of socio-pedagogical requirements, constantly depend on changes taking place in the economic, social and cultural life of society. These changes require the reorganization of all preschool organizations. In this regard, the role of preschool institutions in the system of continuing education is also of particular importance.

The existing system of preschool institutions in Uzbekistan does not meet modern requirements for demographic, socio-economic and pedagogical impact. Therefore, well-established methods of its construction when organizing a network of modern preschool educational organizations are necessary to take into account the possible dynamics of the population. Further development of the social sphere requires the creation of a typological model of a network of preschool educational institutions based on information about the socio-demographic composition of the population, family composition and lifestyle.

The main part. The problem of rational use of residential areas of cities and villages of Uzbekistan, as well as the trend of individualization of the housing stock of modern urban planning policy, suggests the need to search for modern methods of placing preschool educational organizations in residential areas.

The types of buildings of preschool educational organizations existing at the present stage do not meet the tasks set in practice, since they are represented by separate objects with a typical capacity and have a limited, unified character.

In this regard, the development of new principles for the construction of the preschool educational organizations network, the expansion of building types, as well as improving the quality of architectural and planning solutions is of particular importance.

When designing preschool educational organizations in Uzbekistan, attention is paid mainly to the natural environment of the republic, mainly its architectural appearance, compositional solution, factors that also affect the visual perception of children and their psychological state. The environment in which the buildings of preschool educational organizations spend mostly a long time should correspond to their main functions.

While day groups of the general type of preschool children's organizations, which are the most public, are

usually located in residential neighborhoods or neighborhoods from the architectural side, only work should serve the population in the districts and be within a distance limited by the main streets. Specially designed types of preschool organizations, namely sanatorium and summer kindergartens, are usually considered, as a rule, the most suitable for remote areas of the city in a climate with a temperate climate and natural environment. The service radius of kindergartens should be within 300-350 m, and in expanded complexes - 500 m. It is proposed to build children's organizations for at least 140 places in the city, 90 places in urban-type settlements and at least 50 places in rural settlements (Pic. 1). [7]

Daily or weekly preschool organizations in different countries of the world provide services to preschool children in a periodic form in cooperation with families. In some cases, this situation is significant for the population of the city, and the situation with the provision of services to preschool educational organizations is not normalized.

In areas with a population of more than 4,000 people, in 4-5-storey buildings, it is advisable to choose kindergartens for 280 and 330 places, which in most cases are convenient from the point of view of construction and economy. Where the population is less than 4,000 people, children's flat beds for 140 and 190 beds can be additionally selected. Preschool institutions are located on separate plots, the most convenient, isolated, ventilated and landscaped territories are selected for them. The perimeter of the territory should be surrounded by a protective strip of green spaces, placing this border at a distance of at least 10 m from residential buildings. [6]

When choosing a construction site for a building of preschool organizations, it is necessary to pay great attention to the cleanliness of the land, its sanitary condition, good ventilation and sunbathing, the absence of flooding, waterlogging, as close as possible to groundwater.

In the architectural design of preschool organizations, the projected territory should not be adjacent to outbuildings, kitchens, boiler rooms, garages, parking lots and other similar buildings of shops with poor sanitary conditions that spread unpleasant odors from themselves. They should not be built even in the case of standing ponds, garbage heaps,

cemeteries, rural production and livestock farms, animal storage sites and livestock farms, animal storage sites and near pastures for livestock without a protective zone. A street in residential areas of preschool educational organizations buildings must have a limit of at least 15 m from the red line inside highways. At the same time, the main children's rooms (the play – dining room and the room for groups) should be oriented to the south or to the southeast and east. Children's rooms cannot be rotated to the north and northwest of the Hecht time. [7]

The service area of preschool educational organizations is an integral part of the children's institution. Here children play, play sports, sleep, take water treatments, sun and air baths in summer, walk, sledding and skiing in winter. Taking care of plants and animals, children get acquainted with nature here, acquire initial work skills.

All significant problems in the implementation of the project should be carefully taken into account when planning the territory. In connection with them, the territory must have sufficient dimensions, appropriate equipment and housing.

The plot area is taken in the size of one place: in the ITC - in kindergartens for 90 places - 40 m²; for 140 - 320 places - in complexes for 35 m², 560 and 640 places - 30 m²; in places with a harsh cold climate, the land area can be reduced to 25 m² per place.

In recent years, due to the development of new forms of providing amateur services to the population, as well as public buildings and public complexes within the framework of primary consumer services, hotel-type housing and utilities, the appearance of residential buildings from 16 floors to 51 floors, a new type of activity is being established: non-governmental, private, family preschool educational institutions. [3]

Preschool educational organizations have a well-maintained territory, which includes: a child's physical development zone, a play area, an emotional development zone, a musical (theatrical) zone, a visual activity zone, a play area, a speech development zone, a natural zone, a role-playing games zone, an experiment zone and a book zone [3; 7]. In this case, the individuality of the design and its associative perception prevail, which should cause positive emotions in children.

Conclusion. When designing preschool educational organizations, special importance is attached to the architectural appearance and compositional solution of the building itself into the environment, improving the quality of architectural and planning solutions. Therefore, when designing a kindergarten, it is necessary to take into account the radii of public services in urban and rural areas. This not only contributes to the creation of comfort in urban and rural environments, but it is also necessary to take into account the problem of creating a protected area. [6]

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